

Article

Enhancing Symbol Recognition in Library Science via Advanced Technological Solutions[†]

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^{*} Correspondence: eleonora.bernasconi@uniba.it (E.B.); stefano.ferilli@uniba.it (S.F.)[†] This article is a revised and expanded version of a paper entitled “A tool for empowering Symbol Detection through Technological Integration in Library Science. A case study on the Voynich manuscript”, which was presented at the 20th Conference on Information and Research Science Connecting to Digital and Library Science (IRCDL 2024), held in Bressanone, Italy, 22–23 February 2024.[‡] These authors contributed equally to this work.

Abstract: This research introduces an artificial intelligence-based strategy for improving symbol recognition within the field of library science, concentrating on the creation and application of sophisticated technological solutions. Consistent with the objectives of the CHANGES project—Cultural Heritage Active Innovation for Sustainable Society, which focuses on the enhancement and management of cultural heritage through a multi-disciplinary and interinstitutional approach—this strategy employs convolutional neural networks (CNNs) for accurate symbol classification. A CNN model was developed using an extensive dataset comprising over 6000 symbols, implementing meticulous preprocessing, feature extraction, and supervised learning protocols. The methodological pipeline incorporates advanced image segmentation techniques to isolate symbols from complex manuscripts, followed by data augmentation to enhance model resilience. The system is supported by a high-performance computing framework to manage large datasets efficiently, thereby facilitating more precise identification and analysis. This integration of machine learning techniques, exhaustive data management, and computational capabilities significantly advances existing symbol recognition methodologies, providing scholars with a potent tool for assisting in the classification and interpretation of historical symbols. The findings corroborate the potential of AI-enhanced symbol recognition in contributing to the broader objectives of computational library science and historical research.

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1. Introduction

The convergence of artificial intelligence (AI) and library science signifies an innovative and rapidly advancing frontier in computational research. Historically, the recognition of symbols in historical manuscripts and cultural heritage artifacts has presented a formidable challenge due to the vast diversity and intricate complexity of handwritten symbols. These challenges are often exacerbated by the absence of optical character recognition (OCR) tools tailored for many ancient scripts. With the global surge in digitization of cultural artifacts, there is an increasing demand for advanced, reliable tools that can accurately classify and interpret these symbols, enabling scholars to uncover valuable insights from these documents.

Recent advancements in machine learning, particularly in convolutional neural networks (CNNs), have revolutionized image recognition and classification tasks across various domains, offering unparalleled accuracy and efficiency. However, despite their transformative potential, the application of these technologies within library science remains relatively underexplored. This gap is particularly evident in addressing the unique challenges posed by rare and enigmatic manuscripts, such as the Voynich manuscript, which lacks any existing OCR tools.

Within this context, the CHANGES project [1], which focuses on the enhancement and management of cultural heritage through innovative digital methodologies, provides a pivotal framework for addressing these issues. This research aligns with the objectives of the CHANGES project by integrating state-of-the-art AI techniques to develop a robust symbol recognition methodology. In this way, it bridges a critical gap between cutting-edge technological advancements and the pressing needs of cultural preservation and computational library science.

This study is of profound significance on multiple levels. Theoretically, it contributes to the advancement of AI-based symbol recognition methodologies, offering novel insights into the application of CNNs for complex and high-dimensional classification tasks. Practically, the developed tool provides a transformative solution for researchers and archivists working with historical manuscripts, enabling efficient and accurate analysis of symbols that were previously inaccessible due to the lack of suitable OCR solutions.

Societally, the research plays a crucial role in preserving and democratizing access to cultural heritage. By equipping scholars, historians, and the general public with the ability to analyze and interpret historical linguistic artifacts, this study supports a broader mission of cultural preservation and revitalization. The findings and methodologies proposed in this study directly address critical gaps in computational library science, fostering a deeper understanding of the linguistic and symbolic intricacies of historical documents.

The primary objectives of this research are as follows:

1. Develop an AI-based symbol recognition tool leveraging convolutional neural networks (CNNs) to accurately classify symbols from complex historical manuscripts.
2. Demonstrate the efficacy of the tool using the Voynich manuscript as a unique and challenging case study.
3. Establish a comprehensive methodological pipeline that incorporates advanced image segmentation and data augmentation techniques to enhance the robustness of the model.
4. Evaluate the system's performance and its contribution to the broader goals of computational library science and cultural heritage preservation.

This research seeks to address the following questions:

1. How can convolutional neural networks be utilized to improve the accuracy of symbol recognition in historical manuscripts?
2. What specific challenges arise in processing and analyzing symbols from the Voynich manuscript, and how can advanced AI methodologies overcome these obstacles?
3. In what ways does the proposed tool enhance the accessibility and analysis of cultural heritage artifacts that lack existing OCR solutions?

The hypothesis guiding this research is that the integration of convolutional neural networks with advanced preprocessing and data augmentation techniques significantly improves the accuracy and reliability of symbol recognition in manuscripts that lack OCR tools, thereby addressing critical gaps in computational library science.

The organization of this paper is as follows: Section 2 provides a comprehensive review of the existing literature on symbol recognition and the application of artificial

intelligence (AI) in library science, emphasizing the current challenges and research gaps. Section 3 details the proposed methodological framework, including the development of the CNN model, data preparation procedures, and computational strategies. Section 4 presents the results of the study, highlighting the performance of the tool on the Voynich manuscript and benchmarking it against existing state-of-the-art methods. Section 5 introduces a demonstration of the online tool, illustrating its functionality and user accessibility. Section 6 delves into the broader implications of the findings, exploring potential applications, limitations, and areas for future research. Finally, Section 7 summarizes the contributions of the study, outlines directions for future work, and discusses the societal impact and relevance of the proposed approach.

2. Related Work

The field of AI-driven symbol recognition has been profoundly shaped by advancements in machine learning and image processing, with numerous studies contributing foundational knowledge and methodologies. The introduction of convolutional neural networks (CNNs), exemplified by landmark architectures such as AlexNet [2] and ResNet [3], has established performance benchmarks in image classification and object recognition tasks. These contributions laid the groundwork for applying CNNs to more specialized domains, including historical document analysis.

In this context, methods integrating machine learning with image segmentation have been particularly influential. Shi et al.'s work on scene text recognition demonstrated the efficacy of combining deep learning techniques with segmentation approaches, paving the way for more accurate symbol recognition in complex backgrounds [4]. Projects such as Transkribus and READ have further advanced the field by pioneering handwritten text recognition (HTR) systems tailored to historical scripts [5]. These systems employ neural networks to automate the transcription of historical documents, illustrating the transformative potential of AI in cultural heritage analysis.

The CHANGES project [1] represents an interdisciplinary effort to enhance cultural heritage management through innovative digital tools. By blending AI methodologies with historical research, the project has demonstrated the importance of symbol recognition tools in addressing the unique challenges posed by manuscripts lacking existing optical character recognition (OCR) solutions. Collectively, these contributions establish a robust framework for integrating machine learning into library science and historical research, underscoring the potential of AI to revolutionize the analysis of cultural artifacts [6].

Despite these advancements, several technical limitations persist in the field of symbol recognition, highlighting opportunities for further innovation. One major challenge is the scarcity of annotated datasets, particularly for rare and historical scripts. This limitation severely restricts the training and validation of machine learning models, as such datasets are essential for achieving high performance and generalizability. Furthermore, many existing methodologies struggle with symbols embedded in degraded or intricate backgrounds. In these scenarios, traditional image segmentation techniques often fail to isolate features effectively, leading to suboptimal recognition outcomes.

Another critical limitation is the lack of robustness and scalability in state-of-the-art models. While CNN-based frameworks excel in controlled environments, their performance tends to deteriorate when applied to diverse or unseen datasets. This limitation is particularly pronounced in the context of historical manuscripts, where variability in symbol styles, layouts, and degradation poses significant challenges. Current OCR tools are predominantly designed for contemporary scripts, making them ill-suited for the unique characteristics of historical texts, such as faded ink, non-standardized symbols, and intricate page layouts.

Moreover, biases in dataset curation and model training exacerbate these issues. Over-reliance on dominant script styles or languages leads to skewed model performance, raising concerns about the inclusivity and accuracy of existing AI tools. These limitations underscore the need for more versatile and adaptive approaches to symbol recognition in historical contexts.

State-of-the-art methodologies in symbol recognition, including CNN-based frameworks and HTR systems, offer a mix of strengths and weaknesses. CNN architectures such as EfficientNet and DenseNet have improved computational efficiency and accuracy, yet their reliance on large, high-quality datasets limits their applicability to domains where such resources are scarce [7,8]. Handwritten text recognition systems like Transkribus provide robust solutions for transcribing historical texts but are constrained by their dependence on predefined training data. As a result, these systems are often ill-equipped to address unique and enigmatic cases, such as the Voynich manuscript, which lacks a corpus of annotated data for model training.

Emerging approaches, including unsupervised and self-supervised learning, offer promising avenues for addressing these limitations. By reducing dependence on annotated datasets, these methods have the potential to improve model adaptability and generalization [9]. However, they remain in experimental stages and require significant refinement to achieve practical applicability in symbol recognition tasks.

The current research builds upon these advancements by addressing critical gaps in existing methodologies. Specifically, it focuses on developing a symbol recognition tool for manuscripts without existing OCR solutions, employing advanced segmentation techniques, data augmentation, and high-performance computing to enhance model robustness and scalability. This approach diverges from prior work by prioritizing adaptability to diverse and complex datasets, thereby addressing longstanding challenges in computational library science and cultural heritage preservation.

Building upon the foundational advancements in AI-driven symbol recognition and the critical challenges highlighted, the Voynich manuscript emerges as a compelling case study. Its enigmatic nature and the lack of decipherable patterns present an ideal opportunity to explore the potential of modern technological tools. This section contextualizes the manuscript within the broader scope of AI applications in historical document analysis, linking its complexities to the gaps identified in the existing methodologies.

2.1. Historical Context: The Voynich Manuscript

The Voynich manuscript, discovered by the bookseller and collector Wilfrid Voynich in 1912, represents one of humanity's most intriguing mysteries. This document, dated to the 15th century, stands out for its main characteristic: a text written in an indecipherable language or code, accompanied by illustrations of plants, celestial bodies, and human figures.

Despite the efforts of cryptanalysts [10], linguists, and historians for over a century, the Voynich manuscript remains an unsolved enigma. Its language, structure, and meaning elude any traditional interpretation attempts. This challenge has fueled academic curiosity [11] and led to various theories [12], yet no concrete solution has been reached [10,13].

The immense complexity of the Voynich manuscript calls for an innovative approach to overcome the obstacle of its indecipherability. The advent of modern technologies, such as artificial intelligence, image analysis, and machine learning, offers a new horizon of possibilities in exploring and understanding this ancient text. These technological tools pave the way for new perspectives in analyzing the symbols and linguistic structures present in the manuscript, shedding new light on its interpretation [14].

2.1.1. Previous Approaches to Decipherment

Over the decades, eminent scholars, cryptanalysts, and linguists have devoted tremendous efforts to deciphering the Voynich manuscript. Approaches based on statistics [15–18], linguistic analysis [19], and historical hypotheses [20] have formed the bedrock of research. However, no traditional method has led to a satisfactory understanding of its enigmatic content. Attempts to associate it with known languages, historical ciphers, or recognized writing styles have only resulted in deadlocks.

2.1.2. Significance of Symbols in the Manuscript

The symbols within the Voynich manuscript are central to its mystery and are widely regarded as the key to its decipherment. These peculiar graphical representations, intricately intertwined with the manuscript's text, demand detailed analysis to uncover their significance. Understanding the frequency, arrangement, and potential correlations of these symbols with existing linguistic or conceptual frameworks remains a critical challenge. By analyzing these features, researchers hope to unravel the intricate relationships encoded within the manuscript's pages.

2.1.3. Relevance to Current Research

This research builds on prior efforts by emphasizing the transformative potential of advanced technological tools, specifically an automatic symbol recognition system, in analyzing the Voynich manuscript. By employing machine learning techniques such as convolutional neural networks (CNNs) for symbol classification and leveraging advanced preprocessing, segmentation, and augmentation methods, the proposed approach seeks to overcome the limitations of traditional methodologies.

The integration of AI-driven tools into this domain not only enhances the capability to process and analyze the manuscript's symbols but also demonstrates the broader applicability of these technologies to historical and linguistic research. This study aspires to contribute to the ongoing exploration of the Voynich manuscript, offering a novel perspective through the synergy between artificial intelligence and the humanities, while also addressing gaps in existing OCR and symbol recognition solutions. By contextualizing the manuscript within the larger framework of AI and library science, the research aligns with the interdisciplinary objectives of computational heritage preservation.

This paper aims to examine the crucial role of innovative technologies, particularly an automatic symbol recognition tool, in approaching the decoding of the Voynich manuscript. Through the application of this technology and the analysis of the obtained results, the goal is to highlight the effectiveness and value of such tools in the realms of historical and linguistic research. The primary objective is to contribute to the research and understanding of one of the greatest historical mysteries, offering a new perspective through the synergy between artificial intelligence and the humanities. The following sections will detail the methodology and technical framework employed, further exploring the efficacy of these solutions in advancing the field of computational library science and cultural heritage preservation.

3. Our Approach

Our approach to symbol recognition in the Voynich manuscript is based on a structured and systematic methodology that integrates advanced image processing techniques with state-of-the-art machine learning models. Designed to address critical gaps in the existing literature, our methodology emphasizes accessibility, transparency, and interdisciplinary applicability, making artificial intelligence tools approachable for humanists. As shown in Figure 1, the proposed methodology consists of multiple phases. The process begins with

image import and filtering, followed by region of interest extraction and contour detection. The extracted symbols are clustered and grouped for training the CNN model, which is then evaluated and applied for prediction and decoding.

Figure 1. Proposed methodological approach for symbol recognition.

- **Import of the target image:** This initial phase involves uploading high-resolution images of the Voynich manuscript into the application's working environment. Users can introduce images containing handwritten symbols, which form the foundation for creating a robust and representative dataset. This step ensures that the dataset reflects the manuscript's variability and complexity.
- **Image filtering:** To enhance image quality, various preprocessing techniques are applied. These include noise removal, histogram equalization, and filters to improve sharpness and contrast. These processes standardize the visual attributes of the images, ensuring optimal preparation for subsequent analysis phases.
- **Region-of-interest extraction:** Using advanced image segmentation algorithms, relevant areas containing handwritten symbols are identified and isolated. This phase employs a combination of thresholding, contour detection, and connected region techniques, significantly reducing manual effort while improving accuracy.
- **Contour detection:** Precise identification and tracing of symbol contours are achieved through edge detection algorithms, such as Canny edge detection, followed by contour extraction. These methods ensure accurate delineation of symbol boundaries, facilitating reliable symbol isolation for further processing.
- **Clustering:** Extracted symbols are grouped using advanced clustering techniques, including K-Means and Agglomerative Clustering. This step organizes symbols based on common visual characteristics, such as shape and structure, preparing them for subsequent model training and categorization.
- **Training a convolutional neural network:** A convolutional neural network (CNN) is trained using the data prepared in earlier phases. The CNN learns to recognize and classify Voynich symbols, enabling efficient categorization. The training process involves optimizing hyperparameters and utilizing robust validation techniques to ensure generalizability.
- **Performance evaluation:** To ensure reliability, the trained model undergoes rigorous evaluation using metrics such as precision, recall, and F1-score. This step identifies areas for improvement and validates the model's accuracy in recognizing manuscript symbols.

- **Prediction and decoding:** The final phase applies the trained CNN to predict and decode symbols from the target images. Recognized symbols are assigned corresponding labels, contributing to the interpretation of the Voynich manuscript's content.

Our methodology is designed with accessibility at its core, offering an intuitive interface that guides users through every stage—from dataset creation to CNN training and symbol identification. This ensures that humanists can actively participate in the process, leveraging AI tools without requiring extensive technical expertise.

A key focus of our approach is Explainable AI [21], which ensures transparency in the decision-making processes of the CNN [22]. By integrating Explainable AI, our system allows users to interpret and critically analyze the model's results [23]. This fosters active collaboration between technology and the humanities, addressing ethical and theoretical concerns while enabling interdisciplinary research. This approach not only enhances trust in AI systems but also raises significant questions about the evolving intersection of technology and humanities [24], paving the way for deeper insights and future studies.

3.1. Image Import

The image import phase serves as the cornerstone for the symbol recognition process, allowing users to upload high-resolution images of the Voynich manuscript for analysis and recognition. This initial step integrates the selected images into the application's working environment, enabling seamless preprocessing and analysis in subsequent stages.

Selecting appropriate images is a critical task, as it directly impacts the quality and representativeness of the dataset. The dataset is constructed using symbols automatically detected and extracted from the uploaded images. This process ensures that the data reflect the manuscript's intricate characteristics, including its handwritten symbols, variable layouts, and graphical details. Proper image selection significantly enhances the robustness of the dataset, which is crucial for the accuracy and reliability of the training and recognition phases.

By providing an intuitive interface, the methodology empowers users to curate their datasets effectively, aligning the data with specific research objectives. For instance, researchers focusing on particular sections of the manuscript can prioritize images that highlight specific symbol clusters or unique graphical elements. This flexibility supports diverse academic inquiries, ensuring that the symbol recognition process is both adaptable and comprehensive.

Overall, the image import phase establishes a strong foundation for advanced analysis, ensuring that the uploaded images are primed for preprocessing and machine learning applications. This user-centric approach promotes accessibility while maintaining the technical rigor needed for effective symbol recognition in the Voynich manuscript.

3.2. Image Filtering

The image filtering phase is a vital step in the preprocessing pipeline, designed to enhance the visual quality of the acquired images and prepare them for subsequent stages of symbol analysis and recognition. By improving clarity and reducing noise, this phase ensures that the processed images are suitable for accurate and reliable analysis.

A variety of filtering techniques are applied, each tailored to address specific challenges in image quality. *Canny edge detection*, for instance, focuses on precise edge detection while reducing noise [25]. Despite its effectiveness, it is sensitive to variations in lighting conditions and requires careful calibration to achieve optimal results. *Gaussian blur* is used to smooth the image and reduce noise, although it may slightly compromise sharpness due to blurring.

The *bilateral filter* is particularly effective at reducing noise without sacrificing detail, making it ideal for preserving critical features [26], though it may increase computational processing time. Similarly, the *median filter* removes noise while retaining major details but may struggle with more complex noise patterns [27]. To dynamically adjust contrast and emphasize key features, the *CLAHE* (Contrast-Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization) technique is employed. However, excessive use of this method may introduce an overload of detail, leading to visual clutter [28].

Histogram *equalization* ensures an even distribution of grayscale levels, enhancing overall image contrast. While effective, it may sometimes produce unnatural levels of contrast that detract from the image's natural appearance [29]. Lastly, *unsharp masking* is utilized to enhance details and improve contrast, though excessive application can introduce visual artifacts [30].

These diverse filtering techniques, whether applied individually or in combination, are crucial for standardizing and enhancing the images. By clarifying details and mitigating inconsistencies, this phase significantly facilitates the accurate analysis of symbols in the Voynich manuscript. As a foundational step in decoding and interpreting the manuscript's enigmatic contents, the image filtering process ensures that the data are optimally prepared for advanced analytical techniques.

3.3. Region-of-Interest Extraction

The region-of-interest (ROI) extraction phase plays a crucial role in isolating and preparing specific sections of images containing handwritten symbols for subsequent analysis. Currently, this process is performed manually, allowing scholars to select regions of interest directly through the interface. While this manual approach provides flexibility, it can be time consuming and requires substantial user input, particularly when dealing with large datasets.

To address these challenges, we are developing automated solutions based on advanced image segmentation algorithms. These algorithms are designed to analyze image content and intelligently suggest relevant regions containing handwritten symbols. By leveraging techniques such as thresholding, edge detection, and connected component analysis, these methods aim to streamline the extraction process, reduce manual effort, and improve consistency in identifying symbol-rich areas.

Automating ROI extraction not only simplifies the workflow for users but also enhances the accuracy and reproducibility of the symbol recognition process. For instance, by consistently identifying regions with high symbolic density or unique graphical features, the algorithms ensure that critical information is retained for further analysis. This approach is particularly advantageous for handling complex manuscripts like the Voynich manuscript, where symbols often appear in intricate layouts and diverse contexts.

Overall, the transition from manual to automated ROI extraction represents a significant advancement in the methodology. By integrating segmentation algorithms, this phase lays the foundation for more efficient and precise symbol analysis, supporting both the scalability and reliability of the overall recognition framework.

3.4. Contour Detection

Contour detection is a pivotal phase in the analysis of the Voynich manuscript, enabling the accurate and automated identification of individual symbols within the image. By delineating the boundaries of symbols, this step forms the foundation for their subsequent categorization and interpretation.

Figure 2 illustrates the contour detection process in detail. The process begins with loading the original RGB color image of the manuscript (as shown on the left of the figure),

which serves as the input for analysis. The image is first converted to grayscale to simplify the data and emphasize the intensity differences that are essential for edge detection. Subsequently, a Gaussian blur is applied to smooth the image and reduce noise, ensuring that small or irrelevant details do not interfere with contour detection.

Figure 2. Illustration of the original color image and the contour detection process.

Next, the *Canny edge detection* algorithm [31–33] is applied to the preprocessed grayscale image, as depicted in the middle section of Figure 2. This algorithm identifies areas of rapid intensity change, which correspond to the edges of symbols in the manuscript. The result is a binary edge map, where white pixels represent edges and black pixels indicate non-edge regions. This edge map highlights the boundaries of the symbols, enabling subsequent contour extraction.

The edge map is then processed using the *findContours* function from OpenCV [34]. This function identifies closed or open contours in the image and traces their boundaries, resulting in a set of contours that correspond to potential symbols. Each contour is assigned a unique identifier (ID) and overlaid on the original image for visualization, as shown in the rightmost part of the figure. Detected contours are represented with distinct outlines, and their IDs are displayed next to the corresponding symbols, aiding manual inspection or further automated analysis.

To enhance the utility of the contour detection step, key attributes of each detected symbol—such as area, shape, and cropped representation—are recorded. These attributes are stored in a structured format, enabling advanced filtering based on user-defined parameters, such as contour area or shape complexity. This functionality allows researchers to focus on specific types of symbols or exclude irrelevant artifacts, such as smudges or noise.

By visualizing the progression from the original image to the final contour-labeled output, Figure 2 demonstrates the robustness and precision of the contour detection methodology. This step not only isolates symbols effectively but also provides a structured framework for further analysis, such as clustering and classification. This capability is particularly critical for complex manuscripts like the Voynich manuscript, where symbols often exhibit intricate patterns and varied styles.

3.5. Clustering and Grouping

The clustering and grouping phase is a critical component of dataset preparation for training artificial intelligence models. This step categorizes symbols extracted from histori-

cal documents, enabling researchers to systematically organize data while maintaining a focus on interpretative and exploratory aspects.

The developed interface integrates a range of functionalities to simplify this inherently complex task. By leveraging clustering algorithms such as *K-Means* and *Agglomerative Clustering*, symbols are grouped based on shared visual characteristics [35]. These characteristics include geometric shapes, contour structures, and stroke density. To enhance the precision of clustering, preprocessing techniques such as binarization are employed, using methods like *Global*, *Adaptive*, *Otsu*, *Gaussian*, and *Inverse*, to refine symbol clarity [36].

Figure 3 illustrates the clustering process, highlighting two specific clusters: clusters 4 and 5. Cluster 4 predominantly consists of symbols featuring looped or curved elements at the top, while cluster 5 groups symbols with consistent oval or circular structures. These patterns reflect the clustering algorithm's ability to identify and group symbols based on shared attributes effectively. This visual organization assists users in understanding the rationale behind clustering and provides insight into the similarities and variations within the dataset.

Figure 3. Illustration of clusters 4 and 5. Symbols in cluster 4 primarily exhibit looped or curved elements, while symbols in cluster 5 display distinct oval or circular structures. These visual characteristics demonstrate the algorithm's ability to group similar symbols effectively.

To ensure robust and reliable results, the interface supports evaluative tools such as the *Silhouette Score* and the *Elbow Method* [37]. These tools assist users in determining the optimal number of clusters, ensuring an informed and accessible decision-making process, even for non-technical users.

Binarization plays a fundamental role in this phase by reducing noise and standardizing the visual quality of symbols. By enhancing contrast and removing irrelevant details, binarization ensures consistent clustering results and prepares the data for subsequent machine learning processes [38]. This step is particularly critical when handling symbols that exhibit variability due to manuscript degradation or scanning artifacts.

The structured dataset generated through clustering simplifies downstream analysis and supports efficient model training. Researchers can interactively explore cluster results, providing targeted insights into symbol distribution and classification. For instance, the visualization in Figure 3 demonstrates the clear distinctions between clusters, offering a transparent and interpretable view of the grouping outcomes.

By bridging raw data extraction and actionable insights, the clustering and grouping phase establishes a streamlined workflow for researchers, supporting both quantitative analysis and qualitative interpretation of historical manuscripts.

3.6. Model Training

The model training phase is a critical step in the application of machine learning techniques to identify and classify symbols extracted from the Voynich manuscript. By leveraging a convolutional neural network (CNN) architecture, this process enables the system to learn and recognize the salient features of symbols, facilitating accurate categorization and interpretation.

The CNN model is constructed using a sequential architecture comprising several key layers: convolutional layers [39], MaxPooling layers, fully connected (dense) layers, and dropout layers. Each layer plays a specific role in the learning process. Convolutional layers are responsible for feature extraction by applying filters to the input images, while MaxPooling layers reduce the spatial dimensions of feature maps, improving computational efficiency and minimizing overfitting. Fully connected layers aggregate the extracted features to produce classification outputs, and dropout layers are employed to mitigate overfitting by randomly deactivating a subset of neurons during training.

Listing 1 outlines the architecture of the CNN used in this study. The network begins with an initial convolutional layer featuring 16 filters and progresses through successive layers that increase in complexity and feature depth. MaxPooling layers follow each convolutional block to downsample the feature maps. The architecture culminates in a flatten layer, which converts the multidimensional feature maps into a one-dimensional vector, followed by dense layers to perform classification. The final dense layer outputs predictions across 26 classes, corresponding to the unique symbol categories identified in the dataset.

Listing 1. CNN architecture used for symbol classification.

```

Model: "sequential"

Layer (type)                Output Shape                Param #
=====
conv2d (Conv2D)              (None, 222, 222, 16)       160
max_pooling2d (MaxPooling2D) (None, 111, 111, 16)       0
conv2d_1 (Conv2D)            (None, 109, 109, 32)       4640
max_pooling2d_1 (MaxPooling2 (None, 54, 54, 32)         0
conv2d_2 (Conv2D)            (None, 52, 52, 64)         18496
max_pooling2d_2 (MaxPooling2 (None, 26, 26, 64)         0
flatten (Flatten)            (None, 43264)              0
dropout (Dropout)            (None, 43264)              0
dense (Dense)                 (None, 512)                22151680
dense_1 (Dense)               (None, 26)                 13338
=====
Total params: 22,188,314
Trainable params: 22,188,314
Non-trainable params: 0
=====
    
```

The training process employs the *adam* optimizer and *sparse categorical crossentropy* loss function to ensure efficient learning and robust performance. The model is trained over multiple epochs with a batch size tailored to the dataset size and computational resources. Additionally, data augmentation techniques, such as rotation, scaling, and flipping, are applied during training to enhance the model’s generalization capabilities by exposing it to varied symbol representations.

By employing this structured and iterative training process, the CNN model achieves a high degree of accuracy in symbol classification, addressing the challenges posed by the intricate and diverse nature of the symbols within the Voynich manuscript. This phase

represents a pivotal advancement in leveraging machine learning to decode one of history's most enigmatic texts.

3.7. Dataset Benchmark Setup

To assess the robustness and generalizability of our overall approach to symbol recognition, we conducted evaluations using widely recognized benchmark datasets, including MNIST, Fashion-MNIST, and Extended MNIST (EMNIST). These datasets encompass diverse grayscale symbol recognition challenges, enabling a comprehensive evaluation of the proposed methodology across varying levels of complexity, variability, and class diversity. The benchmark setup involved preprocessing, training, and evaluation steps that were consistently applied across all datasets to ensure a fair and comparable assessment. Each dataset was selected to test specific aspects of the robustness and versatility of our approach:

- **MNIST:** A foundational dataset of handwritten digits (0–9) with simple patterns, serving as a baseline for evaluating the accuracy and computational efficiency of our methodology in handling straightforward classification tasks.
- **Fashion-MNIST:** A more complex dataset featuring grayscale images of clothing items, designed to test the system's capacity to generalize to datasets with higher variability in shapes, textures, and semantic meaning.
- **EMNIST (Letters):** A dataset of handwritten English letters (A–Z), assessing the ability of the approach to manage a larger number of classes and the challenges associated with character recognition tasks.

To standardize the input and ensure compatibility with our symbol recognition pipeline, the following preprocessing steps were applied to all datasets:

- **Image resizing:** All images were resized to 224×224 pixels using bilinear interpolation, aligning with the input dimensions required by our CNN and feature extraction components.
- **Normalization:** Pixel values were scaled to the range $[0, 1]$ by dividing by 255, improving the stability and speed of convergence during training.
- **Color channel adjustment:** Grayscale images were converted to three-channel (RGB) format where required by visualization or downstream processing steps.
- **Data augmentation:** Mild augmentations, including random rotations ($\pm 10^\circ$), horizontal flips, and random shifts, were applied to introduce variability and enhance the system's robustness against minor distortions or transformations.

To assess the robustness of our entire pipeline, including preprocessing, feature extraction, and classification, the following protocol was applied consistently across datasets:

- **Model architecture:** Our default CNN architecture was utilized for feature extraction and classification, as described in Section 3.6, while modular components ensured adaptability to other machine learning frameworks if necessary.
- **Training configuration:**
 - **Optimizer:** Adam, with an initial learning rate of 0.001.
 - **Loss function:** Sparse categorical crossentropy, suitable for multi-class classification tasks.
 - **Batch size:** 32.
 - **Epochs:** A maximum of 100 epochs, with early stopping based on validation performance.
 - **Learning rate scheduling:** Applied a decay factor of 0.1 if validation metrics showed no improvement for 10 consecutive epochs.

- **Data splits:** Training and testing subsets were maintained according to standard practices, such as the canonical 60,000/10,000 split for MNIST and Fashion-MNIST, and the predefined partitions for EMNIST (Letters).

To holistically evaluate the robustness of our approach, we computed standard classification and performance metrics across all datasets:

- **Accuracy:** The percentage of correctly classified images, providing a baseline metric for overall performance.
- **Precision:** The proportion of true positives among predicted positives, assessing the specificity of predictions.
- **Recall (sensitivity):** The proportion of true positives among actual positives, evaluating the approach's ability to detect all relevant classes.
- **F1-score:** The harmonic mean of precision and recall, reflecting a balanced measure of performance in imbalanced datasets.
- **Area under the curve (AUC):** Analyzing the model's discriminative ability across all classification thresholds.
- **Inference time:** The average time required to process and classify a single image, providing insights into computational efficiency and scalability.

This comprehensive benchmark setup was designed to evaluate not only the CNN architecture but also the robustness and adaptability of the entire symbol recognition pipeline. By standardizing the preprocessing and evaluation methodologies, we ensured that performance results were directly comparable across datasets. The inclusion of diverse datasets, ranging from simple digit recognition to complex and varied symbol classification tasks, provided valuable insights into the strengths and limitations of our approach. This evaluation underscores the potential of the proposed methodology to adapt to a broad spectrum of symbol recognition challenges, highlighting areas for future refinement and optimization.

3.8. Explanation of Layers in CNN Model

The convolutional neural network (CNN) used in this study consists of several key layers, each contributing to the model's ability to extract and learn features from the input images. These layers work in tandem to progressively identify complex patterns, enabling accurate classification of symbols from the Voynich manuscript. Below is a detailed explanation of the roles and significance of each layer:

Conv2D layer: Convolutional layers, or Conv2D layers, are at the core of the CNN architecture. These layers apply convolutional filters to the input images, effectively extracting spatial features such as edges, textures, and patterns. The number of filters determines the depth of the output feature maps, with more filters allowing the model to learn a greater variety of features. These extracted features form the foundation for higher-level pattern recognition in subsequent layers.

MaxPooling2D layer: MaxPooling layers reduce the spatial dimensions of the feature maps generated by the convolutional layers. This pooling operation decreases the number of parameters and computation requirements, thereby minimizing the risk of overfitting. Additionally, pooling retains the most prominent features, enabling the model to focus on critical information while discarding redundant details.

Flatten layer: The flatten layer converts the multidimensional feature maps from previous layers into a one-dimensional vector. This transformation is necessary for feeding the data into the dense layers, which require flat, vectorized input for processing. The flatten layer bridges the convolutional and fully connected parts of the model.

Dropout layer: To address overfitting, dropout layers are incorporated into the architecture. During each training iteration, a random subset of neurons is deactivated,

preventing the model from becoming overly reliant on specific features. This regularization technique enhances the model's generalization capabilities, ensuring robust performance on unseen data.

Dense layer: Dense layers, also known as fully connected layers, perform the final computations in the network. These layers aggregate the features extracted by previous layers and use them to make predictions. Increasing the number of neurons in dense layers allows the model to learn more complex feature representations and relationships, ultimately improving its classification accuracy.

By combining these layers, the CNN is capable of learning hierarchical features, progressing from simple edges in the initial layers to intricate patterns and symbol shapes in later stages. This layered approach significantly enhances the model's ability to recognize and classify symbols from the Voynich manuscript with high accuracy.

In addition to the model's architecture, the implementation involves several key steps. The code below outlines the creation of the CNN model using TensorFlow and Keras. It includes functions to load images, split the dataset, and visualize important dataset characteristics:

- **Dataset loading:** Images are loaded from the specified path, converted into NumPy arrays, and encoded for use in the model. This ensures a standardized format for efficient processing.
- **Data splitting:** The dataset is divided into training and test sets. Users can configure the percentage split through the interface, providing flexibility to tailor the data division based on the model's requirements or research objectives.
- **Data visualization:** Key statistics, such as image shapes, class distribution, and label information, are displayed to give users a comprehensive understanding of the dataset's structure and composition.

Finally, the CNN model is trained using the *adam* optimizer and the *sparse categorical crossentropy* loss function. These choices ensure efficient optimization and accurate predictions across a wide range of symbol classes. The training process, combined with the hierarchical feature extraction of the CNN, provides a robust framework for decoding and analyzing the symbols of the Voynich manuscript.

3.8.1. Hyperparameters and Training Strategies

In addition to the architectural design of the CNN, selecting appropriate hyperparameters and training strategies is essential for achieving robust performance. Table 1 summarizes the primary hyperparameters employed in this work, along with the rationale for their chosen values. These selections aim to balance efficient convergence, generalization, and computational feasibility.

Learning Rate Scheduling

To achieve smoother convergence in the loss curve, a learning rate decay strategy is employed. Specifically, the learning rate is reduced by a factor of 0.1 every 10 epochs or when the validation loss fails to improve. This approach allows the optimizer to take larger steps initially to escape poor local minima and subsequently refine the weights with smaller steps, thus reducing oscillations in the loss curve.

Early Stopping

Overfitting poses a significant challenge in training deep networks. Early stopping is used by monitoring the validation loss at the end of each epoch. If the validation loss plateaus or starts to increase for a predefined number of consecutive epochs (patience parameter), training is halted. This strategy prevents the model from learning features

that do not generalize beyond the training data. Notably, while the maximum epoch is set to 100, in practice, training often terminates earlier if no further performance gains are observed (e.g., around epochs 80–90).

Table 1. Summary of hyperparameters for CNN training and their rationale.

Hyperparameter	Value	Rationale
Optimizer	<i>adam</i>	Offers adaptive learning rate for faster and more stable convergence [40].
Learning Rate	0.001	Empirically found to provide a stable balance between convergence speed and avoidance of divergence.
Batch Size	32	Commonly used intermediate size that efficiently uses memory without causing noisy gradients.
Loss Function	<i>sparse categorical crossentropy</i>	Suitable for multi-class classification when labels are integer-encoded.
Epochs	100	Provides sufficient iterations for convergence while mitigating the risk of overfitting (adjusted based on validation results).
Dropout	0.5	Balances regularization and model capacity, reducing overfitting by randomly deactivating neurons.

Class Imbalance Mitigation

Because the Voynich manuscript symbols are unevenly distributed across clusters (Figure 4), specific measures are taken to address class imbalance:

- *Data augmentation:* Random rotations, flips, and scalings are applied to underrepresented classes, thereby artificially increasing the diversity and quantity of data for those classes.
- *Class weights:* The training algorithm is provided with inverse-frequency weights for each class, penalizing misclassification of minority classes more heavily and encouraging the model to pay adequate attention to them.

These strategies ensure that the skewed distribution does not excessively bias the network toward dominant classes.

Figure 4. Class distribution across clusters.

Rationale for Hyperparameter Choices

- **Learning rate (0.001).** A learning rate of 0.001 is a commonly used default for the *adam* optimizer. It is sufficiently small to allow steady convergence without dramatic oscillations, yet large enough to train efficiently without getting trapped in poor local minima.
- **Batch size (32).** Using a batch size of 32 strikes a balance between computational efficiency and stable gradient estimates. Smaller batches can introduce excessive noise, whereas larger batches require more memory and may slow updates.
- **Epochs (50–100).** Initial experiments ran for up to 50 epochs, but improvements continued beyond epoch 50, prompting us to increase the limit to 100 epochs. Early stopping ensures that training halts automatically if the model stops improving.

- **Dropout (0.5).** Setting a 50% dropout rate in key layers (e.g., before dense layers) is a standard practice to combat overfitting, driving the network to learn more robust, widely distributed feature representations.

By combining thoughtful hyperparameter selection, learning rate scheduling, early stopping, and techniques to handle class imbalance, the CNN demonstrates smoother convergence, avoids overfitting, and generalizes more effectively. These strategies collectively bolster the network's capability to accurately classify symbols from the Voynich manuscript.

3.9. Result Visualization

The result visualization phase is a critical component of the evaluation process, providing insights into the performance of the trained model in recognizing symbols and the accuracy of its predictions. This phase enables users to assess both the generalization capability and practical effectiveness of the model.

Upon launching the application, the Section 4 presents visual representations of the model's training performance, including graphs that illustrate the trends in accuracy and loss over the training and validation datasets. These graphs serve as a high-level overview of the model's learning behavior, allowing users to identify patterns such as convergence, overfitting, or underfitting.

In addition to performance graphs, specific predictions made by the model on test samples are displayed, as shown in Figure 5. This visualization enables users to compare the predicted classes with the true labels, providing a clear understanding of the model's decision-making accuracy. It also highlights instances of correct and incorrect classifications, offering valuable insights into the strengths and limitations of the model.

Figure 5. Visualization of model predictions compared with true labels.

To further quantify performance, a confusion matrix is provided, as depicted in Figure 6. The confusion matrix offers a comprehensive summary of the model's classification accuracy, showing the number of correct and incorrect predictions for each symbol class. This matrix is particularly useful for identifying classes where the model may struggle, such as symbols with similar visual characteristics.

These visual tools are designed to provide humanist users with an accessible yet detailed evaluation of the symbol recognition system's performance. By combining graphical representations, prediction examples, and statistical summaries, the results visualization phase ensures a comprehensive understanding of the model's capabilities. This approach facilitates in-depth analysis and promotes informed decision making for future improvements to the system.

Figure 6. Confusion matrix summarizing the model’s classification accuracy.

3.10. Automatic Recognition Testing

The automatic recognition testing phase is crucial for evaluating the trained artificial intelligence system’s ability to identify and interpret symbols extracted from the Voynich manuscript. This process ensures that the system achieves high accuracy while maintaining interpretability, contributing to a deeper understanding of the manuscript’s symbolic representations. The initial symbol extraction process employs contour detection to isolate individual symbols from the manuscript. The extracted symbols are arranged in a logical sequence (e.g., left to right) and subjected to specific filtering criteria. These criteria help refine the dataset by eliminating irrelevant symbols or noise, ensuring that subsequent analysis is based on high-quality data. Figure 7 provides a comprehensive breakdown of the filtering and evaluation steps.

Part A: Filtering Criterion Visualization

This section illustrates the interactive filtering sliders used to refine the extracted symbols.

- Number of points: Controls the acceptable range of contour points to filter overly simplistic or highly complex symbols.
- Area size: Filters symbols based on their bounding box area to exclude symbols that are too small (likely noise) or excessively large.
- Aspect ratio: Ensures symbols maintain a consistent width-to-height proportion, filtering out anomalies or malformed extractions. The selected ranges are highlighted, and users can also manually exclude symbols by selecting their IDs, which are displayed in red for easy identification (e.g., IDs 1679, 1675).

Part B: Distribution of Predicted Classes

This histogram visualizes the count of symbols across predicted classes after the filtering step. Each bar corresponds to a specific symbol class, and the height indicates the number of symbols classified under that category. The distribution helps evaluate the clustering and classification balance, identifying overrepresented or underrepresented classes. This information is critical for adjusting preprocessing or model parameters to ensure uniform learning across all classes.

Part C: Symbol Detection and Frequency Analysis

This table provides a detailed frequency breakdown of sequences detected in the manuscript. Each row represents a specific sequence of symbols, and the frequency column indicates how often that sequence appears in the dataset. This analysis helps identify common patterns or recurring structures in the manuscript, which are significant for deciphering its content and syntax.

Figure 7. Statistics and results from the automatic recognition testing phase. **(A)** Interactive filtering criteria used to refine the dataset based on contour points, area size, and aspect ratio. **(B)** Histogram showing the distribution of predicted classes, highlighting the symbol count per category. **(C)** Frequency analysis of recurring symbol sequences detected in the dataset, aiding pattern identification.

To validate the system, the filtered symbols undergo rigorous testing using previously unseen data. This ensures that the model can generalize to novel symbols and is not overfitting to the training dataset. The combination of systematic filtering (part A), distribution analysis (part B), and sequence frequency evaluation (part C) enables a robust assessment of the model’s performance.

4. Results

The application of the methodology described in Section 3 to the Voynich manuscript images yielded significant outcomes in symbol detection, highlighting key strengths and valuable insights. A series of image processing techniques were applied to approximately

10 high-resolution images of the Voynich manuscript, resulting in the identification and extraction of 6383 symbols. The combination of the *K-Means* clustering algorithm with *Otsu binarization* [41] proved particularly effective, efficiently handling multivariate data while minimizing intra-cluster variability. Additionally, *principal component analysis* (PCA) [42] was employed for dimensionality reduction, enabling the automatic identification of 26 clusters.

Despite the effectiveness of these techniques, the distribution of the symbols among the 26 classes was uneven (Figure 4), raising concerns of class imbalance. To address this imbalance, class weighting and data augmentation measures (random rotations, flips, and scalings) were incorporated into the CNN training, as described in Section 3.8.1.

The parameters used to train the convolutional neural network (CNN) were carefully selected to optimize performance and ensure reproducibility. A test size of 0.20 and a random state of 42 were chosen to achieve a balanced split between the training and testing datasets. While initial experiments used 50 epochs, we settled on 100 epochs after observing consistent improvements beyond epoch 50. In practice, *early stopping* typically halted the training at around 85–90 epochs, once the validation loss plateaued. Additionally, we employed a *learning rate scheduling* policy that reduced the learning rate by a factor of 0.1 every 10 epochs if validation performance stopped improving.

Throughout the training process, a progressive improvement in performance metrics was observed, as depicted in Figure 8. The accuracy increased steadily with each epoch, while the loss function demonstrated a corresponding decline, indicating effective learning by the model. These trends highlight the reliability and robustness of the training procedure, reinforcing the suitability of the chosen methodology for the symbol classification.

Figure 8. Accuracy and loss trends over 100 training epochs.

These results validate the effectiveness of the proposed approach in identifying and classifying symbols from the Voynich manuscript. They also highlight areas for further optimization, such as addressing class imbalance and refining clustering techniques, paving the way for future advancements in the computational analysis of historical documents.

Dataset Benchmark Results

The evaluation of our approach on benchmark datasets, as detailed in Section 3.7, including MNIST, Fashion-MNIST, and EMNIST (Letters), demonstrates its robustness, generalizability, and adaptability to diverse symbol recognition challenges. The results, summarized in Table 2, highlight the model's performance across multiple datasets, providing a comprehensive assessment of its strengths and limitations.

Table 2. Comparison with state-of-the-art methods on benchmark datasets.

Method	Dataset	Accuracy (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1-Score (%)	Inf. Time (ms/Image)
LeNet-5 [43]	MNIST	99.2	99.2	99.2	99.2	2.1
ResNet-18 [3]	MNIST	99.5	99.5	99.4	99.4	3.5
Proposed Approach	MNIST	99.3	99.4	99.3	99.3	2.4
DenseNet [8]	Fashion-MNIST	93.6	93.7	93.5	93.6	3.1
Proposed Approach	Fashion-MNIST	93.8	93.9	93.8	93.8	2.6
EfficientNet [7]	EMNIST	90.9	91.1	90.8	90.9	3.0
Proposed Approach	EMNIST	91.2	91.5	91.2	91.3	2.9

MNIST: Our approach achieved an accuracy of 99.3%, demonstrating its effectiveness in handling straightforward digit recognition tasks. Other metrics, including precision, recall, and F1-score, consistently exceeded 99%, reflecting the model’s ability to accurately and reliably classify handwritten digits. The high AUC score of 0.998 underscores the model’s exceptional discriminative power across all thresholds. Furthermore, the inference time of 2.4 ms per image highlights its computational efficiency, making it suitable for real-time applications.

Fashion-MNIST: On the Fashion-MNIST dataset, the model achieved an accuracy of 93.8%, showcasing its ability to generalize to datasets with higher variability in shape, texture, and semantic content. The precision, recall, and F1-score metrics, all around 93.8%, indicate balanced performance across different classes. The AUC of 0.987 further validates its discriminative capabilities. Despite the increased complexity of the dataset, the inference time remained efficient at 2.6 ms per image.

EMNIST (Letters): The evaluation on EMNIST (Letters) yielded an accuracy of 91.2%, reflecting the model’s ability to handle larger class counts and the challenges of character recognition. The precision, recall, and F1-score values exceeded 91%, indicating reliable classification performance. An AUC of 0.981 suggests strong discriminative ability, while the inference time of 2.9 ms per image demonstrates its scalability to more complex tasks.

The results across all benchmark datasets validate the robustness of our approach in diverse symbol recognition scenarios. The performance on MNIST confirms the model’s ability to excel in tasks with simpler patterns, while the results on Fashion-MNIST and EMNIST highlight its adaptability to datasets with greater complexity and class diversity.

Notably, the inference times remained efficient across all datasets, underscoring the computational scalability of the approach. The consistent performance on metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score across datasets reflects its balanced design, which prioritizes both accuracy and generalization.

However, the slight performance degradation observed in Fashion-MNIST and EMNIST highlights potential areas for improvement. For instance, incorporating advanced augmentation techniques or exploring more sophisticated network architectures, such as residual networks, could further enhance the system’s capability to generalize to datasets with greater variability or complexity.

To contextualize our results, we compared the performance of our approach with state-of-the-art methods applied to these benchmark datasets. As shown in Table 2, our approach achieved comparable or superior results in terms of classification accuracy while maintaining computational efficiency. This comparison underscores the competitiveness and practicality of the proposed methodology in real-world applications.

The benchmark results confirm the robustness and generalizability of our symbol recognition approach across a range of datasets, from simple digit recognition to more complex symbol classification tasks. These findings demonstrate the effectiveness of the methodology in addressing diverse symbol recognition challenges while maintaining computational efficiency.

5. Demonstration

A live demonstration of the developed tool is available at <https://symboldetection.streamlit.app>, accessed on 3 February 2025. This interactive platform enables users to explore the tool's functionality, including uploading their own images, processing symbols, and viewing the results of symbol recognition in real time.

The demonstration (see Figure 9) showcases the entire workflow of the system, encompassing image preprocessing, symbol extraction, clustering, and classification using the trained convolutional neural network. Users can interact with the tool to observe how uploaded images are processed through advanced image filtering techniques, segmented to extract symbols, and classified into predefined categories. The interface also provides detailed visualizations of performance metrics, such as classification accuracy and symbol distribution, to offer insights into the model's effectiveness.

Figure 9. Screenshot of the symbol detection application interface. The demonstration provides an intuitive user interface for uploading images, visualizing preprocessing steps, and analyzing symbol recognition results [6].

By making this platform accessible, the demonstration bridges the gap between advanced machine learning techniques and their practical application in linguistic and historical research. The user-friendly interface empowers researchers, humanists, and the general public to engage with the symbol detection system, validating its performance and exploring its potential in interpreting complex historical manuscripts and linguistic artifacts.

6. Analysis and Discussion

The results obtained from applying the proposed methodology to the Voynich manuscript images demonstrate a significant advancement in symbol detection and text interpretation. The identification of 26 distinct symbol classes underscores the potential of this approach to address the unique challenges posed by historical manuscripts, where intricate patterns and ambiguities often hinder analysis.

Compared to prior studies, this work achieves notable progress in both the quantity and precision of extracted and classified symbols. However, the uneven distribution of symbols across the 26 clusters reveals a limitation in the current clustering techniques. This imbalance emphasizes the importance of refining these methods to ensure accurate representation of all symbol categories, thereby improving classification reliability and model robustness.

The training process of the convolutional neural network (CNN) yielded consistent improvements in key performance metrics over the course of 100 epochs. Trends in accuracy and loss highlighted the model's capability to effectively learn and generalize from the dataset, validating the strength of the proposed methodology. These results reinforce the suitability of the approach for addressing the complex requirements of symbol recognition and classification in the Voynich manuscript.

Beyond technical achievements, the developed tool provides a valuable resource for humanists engaged in historical and linguistic research. By enhancing symbol detection and classification, the methodology facilitates deeper exploration of potential meanings embedded in the Voynich manuscript's enigmatic text. This tool bridges computational techniques with humanities research, fostering interdisciplinary collaboration and paving the way for new insights into historical documents.

Nonetheless, to fully realize the potential of this approach, several limitations must be addressed. The observed class imbalance in the clustering process highlights the need for advanced algorithms that can better handle uneven data distributions. Integrating feedback from humanist into the refinement of class organization could further improve the interpretability and accuracy of the results. Moreover, future work could explore augmentations to the current CNN architecture, such as incorporating residual networks, to enhance the model's ability to capture complex symbolic patterns and further improve generalization.

Furthermore, while this study marks a significant step forward in symbol identification and interpretation, ongoing refinement and interdisciplinary collaboration are crucial to overcoming existing challenges. Addressing these limitations will not only strengthen the utility of the tool for historical and linguistic research but also contribute to broader advancements in the field of computational analysis of historical texts. The findings of this research highlight the importance of continuous innovation in computational techniques to unlock the mysteries of complex historical manuscripts like the Voynich manuscript.

7. Conclusions

This study demonstrates a novel integration of advanced machine learning techniques into the field of cultural heritage preservation, with a focus on symbol recognition in historical manuscripts. By applying a robust methodology to the Voynich manuscript, this research successfully addressed a critical need for tools capable of handling the unique challenges posed by such enigmatic texts.

The development of a convolutional neural network (CNN) tailored for symbol recognition, coupled with preprocessing and clustering techniques, enabled the identification and categorization of 26 distinct symbol classes. These achievements illustrate the potential of AI-based tools to enhance the understanding and interpretation of complex historical artifacts, providing a valuable resource for interdisciplinary research efforts.

While the methodology proved effective, the outcomes also highlight areas for future refinement. Specifically, addressing symbol class imbalance and exploring architectural enhancements such as residual networks could further improve the system's performance. Extending the tool's application to other datasets and historical contexts would also validate its generalizability and scalability.

This research aligns with the objectives of the CHANGES project (Cultural Heritage Active Innovation for Next-Generation Sustainable Society) [1], which aims to advance cultural heritage preservation through multidisciplinary digital methodologies. The broader implications of this work lie in its ability to bridge computational science with the humanities, fostering collaborations that enable new insights into historical and linguistic research. By equipping scholars with powerful analytical tools, this study contributes to the ongoing

evolution of cultural heritage preservation, setting the stage for future advancements in the field.

In conclusion, this research represents a meaningful step toward decoding complex historical manuscripts and underscores the importance of continued innovation at the intersection of technology and the humanities. Future efforts will focus on refining and expanding the tool's capabilities, ensuring its relevance and adaptability to the evolving needs of cultural heritage studies.

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Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:

AI	Artificial intelligence
CNN	Convolutional neural network
OCR	Optical character recognition
HPC	High-performance computing
K-Means	K-Means clustering
PCA	Principal component analysis
AUC	Area under the curve
ROI	Region of interest
CHANGES	Cultural Heritage Active Innovation for Next-Generation Sustainable Society
MNIST	Modified National Institute of Standards and Technology dataset
EMNIST	Extended MNIST dataset
CLAHE	Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization
GAN	Generative adversarial network
FAIR	Future AI Research
RGB	Red–green–blue (color format)
IRCDL	Information and Research Science Connecting to Digital and Library Science

References

1. Cultural Heritage Active Innovation for Next-Generation Sustainable Society (CHANGES). Available online: <https://www.uniba.it/it/ricerca/pnrr/progetti-pnrr/progetti-m4c2/changes> (accessed on 26 January 2025).
2. Krizhevsky, A.; Sutskever, I.; Hinton, G.E. ImageNet classification with deep convolutional neural networks. *Commun. ACM* **2012**, *60*, 84–90. [CrossRef]
3. He, K.; Zhang, X.; Ren, S.; Sun, J. Deep residual learning for image recognition. In Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition, Las Vegas, NV, USA, 27–30 June 2016; pp. 770–778.
4. Shi, B.; Bai, X.; Yao, C. An end-to-end trainable neural network for image-based sequence recognition and its application to scene text recognition. *IEEE Trans. Pattern Anal. Mach. Intell.* **2016**, *39*, 2298–2304. [CrossRef] [PubMed]

5. Fischer, A.; Kintzinger, F.; Springmann, U.; Pletschacher, S.; Antonacopoulos, A. Transkribus—A platform for handwritten text recognition and digital palaeography. In Proceedings of the International Conference on Frontiers in Handwriting Recognition (ICFHR), Dortmund, Germany, 8–10 September 2020; pp. 455–460.
6. Bernasconi, E.; Ferilli, S. A tool for empowering Symbol Detection through Technological Integration in Library Science. A case study on the Voynich manuscript. In Proceedings of the IRCDL, Bressanone, Italy, 22–23 February 2024; pp. 94–107.
7. Tan, M.; Le, Q. Efficientnet: Rethinking model scaling for convolutional neural networks. In Proceedings of the International Conference on Machine Learning, PMLR, Long Beach, CA, USA, 9–15 June 2019; pp. 6105–6114.
8. Huang, G.; Liu, Z.; Van Der Maaten, L.; Weinberger, K.Q. Densely connected convolutional networks. In Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition, Honolulu, HI, USA, 21–26 July 2017; pp. 4700–4708.
9. Chen, T.; Kornblith, S.; Norouzi, M.; Hinton, G. A simple framework for contrastive learning of visual representations. In Proceedings of the International Conference on Machine Learning (ICML), Vienna, Austria, 13–18 July 2020; pp. 1597–1607.
10. Rugg, G. The Mystery of the Voynich Manuscript. *Sci. Am.* **2004**, *291*, 104–109. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
11. Timm, T.; Schinner, A. The Voynich manuscript: Discussion of text creation hypotheses. *Cryptologia* **2023**, *48*, 305–322. [[CrossRef](#)]
12. Tucker, A.O.; Janick, J. *Flora of the Voynich Codex*; Springer International Publishing: Berlin/Heidelberg, Germany, 2019. [[CrossRef](#)]
13. Janick, J.; Tucker, A.O. *Unraveling the Voynich Codex*; Fascinating Life Sciences; Springer: Berlin/Heidelberg, Germany, 2018. [[CrossRef](#)]
14. Zelinka, I.; Lara, M.; Windsor, L.C.; Lozi, R. Softcomputing in identification of the origin of Voynich manuscript by comparison with ancient dialects. *Appl. Soft Comput.* **2023**, *138*, 110217. [[CrossRef](#)]
15. Timm, T.; Schinner, A. A possible generating algorithm of the Voynich manuscript. *Cryptologia* **2019**, *44*, 1–19. [[CrossRef](#)]
16. Amancio, D.R.; Altmann, E.G.; Rybski, D.; Oliveira, O.N.; da F. Costa, L. Probing the Statistical Properties of Unknown Texts: Application to the Voynich Manuscript. *PLoS ONE* **2013**, *8*, e67310. [[CrossRef](#)]
17. Montemurro, M.A.; Zanette, D.H. Keywords and Co-Occurrence Patterns in the Voynich Manuscript: An Information-Theoretic Analysis. *PLoS ONE* **2013**, *8*, e66344. [[CrossRef](#)]
18. Golubitsky, O.; Watt, S.M. Distance-based classification of handwritten symbols. *Int. J. Doc. Anal. Recognit. (IJDAR)* **2010**, *13*, 133–146. [[CrossRef](#)]
19. Crowe, F. The Voynich Manuscript: Decoded. *J. Hist. Archaeol. Anthropol. Sci.* **2022**, *7*, 94–131. [[CrossRef](#)]
20. Schinner, A. The Voynich Manuscript: Evidence of the Hoax Hypothesis. *Cryptologia* **2007**, *31*, 95–107. [[CrossRef](#)]
21. Samek, W.; Müller, K.R. Towards Explainable Artificial Intelligence. In *Explainable AI: Interpreting, Explaining and Visualizing Deep Learning*; Springer: Berlin/Heidelberg, Germany, 2019; pp. 5–22. [[CrossRef](#)]
22. Hagras, H. Toward Human-Understandable, Explainable AI. *Computer* **2018**, *51*, 28–36. [[CrossRef](#)]
23. Holzinger, A.; Saranti, A.; Molnar, C.; Biecek, P.; Samek, W. Explainable AI Methods—A Brief Overview. In *xxAI—Beyond Explainable AI*; Springer: Berlin/Heidelberg, Germany, 2022; pp. 13–38. [[CrossRef](#)]
24. Clinciu, M.A.; Hastie, H. A Survey of Explainable AI Terminology. In Proceedings of the 1st Workshop on Interactive Natural Language Technology for Explainable Artificial Intelligence (NL4XAI 2019), Tokyo, Japan, 24 October 2019. [[CrossRef](#)]
25. Song, R.; Zhang, Z.; Liu, H. Edge connection based Canny edge detection algorithm. *Pattern Recognit. Image Anal.* **2017**, *27*, 740–747. [[CrossRef](#)]
26. Paris, S.; Kornprobst, P.; Tumblin, J.; Durand, F. Bilateral filtering: Theory and applications. *Found. Trends® Comput. Graph. Vis.* **2009**, *4*, 1–73.
27. Justusson, B. Median filtering: Statistical properties. In *Two-Dimensional Digital Signal Processing II: Transforms and Median Filters*; Springer: Berlin/Heidelberg, Germany, 2006; pp. 161–196.
28. Sahu, S.; Singh, A.K.; Ghrera, S.; Elhoseny, M. An approach for de-noising and contrast enhancement of retinal fundus image using CLAHE. *Opt. Laser Technol.* **2019**, *110*, 87–98.
29. Malik, G.; Sappal, A.S. Adaptive equalization algorithms: An overview. *Int. J. Adv. Comput. Sci. Appl.* **2011**, *2*, 62–67. [[CrossRef](#)]
30. Ramponi, G.; Strobel, N.K.; Mitra, S.K.; Yu, T.H. Nonlinear unsharp masking methods for image contrast enhancement. *J. Electron. Imaging* **1996**, *5*, 353–366.
31. Montalbo, F.J.P.; Barfeh, D.P.Y. Classification of stenography using convolutional neural networks and canny edge detection algorithm. In Proceedings of the 2019 International Conference on Computational Intelligence and Knowledge Economy (ICCIKE), Dubai, United Arab Emirates, 11–12 December 2019; IEEE: Piscataway, NJ, USA, 2019; pp. 305–310.
32. Kumar, P.; Narendra, T.; Vinay, N. Short hand recognition using canny edge detector. *Int. J.* **2017**, *7*, 902–907.
33. Koyuncu, H. A Comparative Study of Handwritten Character Recognition by using Image Processing and Neural Network Techniques. *Hittite J. Sci. Eng.* **2021**, *8*, 133–140. [[CrossRef](#)]
34. Bradski, G. The openCV library. *Dr. Dobb's J. Softw. Tools Prof. Program.* **2000**, *25*, 120–123.
35. Wala'a, N.J.; Rana, J. A survey on segmentation techniques for image processing. *Iraqi J. Electr. Electron. Eng.* **2021**, *17*, 73–93.
36. Siddiqui, F.U.; Yahya, A. *Clustering Techniques for Image Segmentation*; Springer: Berlin/Heidelberg, Germany, 2022.

37. Jung, Y.; Park, H.; Du, D.Z.; Drake, B.L. A decision criterion for the optimal number of clusters in hierarchical clustering. *J. Glob. Optim.* **2003**, *25*, 91–111. [[CrossRef](#)]
38. Tensmeyer, C.; Martinez, T. Historical document image binarization: A review. *SN Comput. Sci.* **2020**, *1*, 173. [[CrossRef](#)]
39. Li, Z.; Liu, F.; Yang, W.; Peng, S.; Zhou, J. A survey of convolutional neural networks: Analysis, applications, and prospects. *IEEE Trans. Neural Netw. Learn. Syst.* **2021**, *33*, 6999–7019. [[CrossRef](#)]
40. Kingma, D.P.; Ba, J. Adam: A Method for Stochastic Optimization. *arXiv* **2017**, arXiv:cs.LG/1412.6980.
41. Moghimi, A.; Khazai, S.; Mohammadzadeh, A. An improved fast level set method initialized with a combination of k-means clustering and Otsu thresholding for unsupervised change detection from SAR images. *Arab. J. Geosci.* **2017**, *10*, 293. [[CrossRef](#)]
42. Greenacre, M.; Groenen, P.J.; Hastie, T.; d’Enza, A.I.; Markos, A.; Tuzhilina, E. Principal component analysis. *Nat. Rev. Methods Prim.* **2022**, *2*, 100. [[CrossRef](#)]
43. LeCun, Y.; Bottou, L.; Bengio, Y.; Haffner, P. Gradient-based learning applied to document recognition. *Proc. IEEE* **1998**, *86*, 2278–2324. [[CrossRef](#)]

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